

Unraveling the Uncommon: Perianal Plasmablastic Lymphoma in an HIV-Negative Patient with Chronic Hepatitis C: A Case Report

Kamran Ahmad^{1*}, Aima Yousaf², Usama Saeed³, Yasir Ali⁴, Shahzad Zafar⁵, Waqar Ali⁶, Mahnosh Saleh⁷

¹Resident Physician, Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar, Pakistan

²Clinical Fellow, George Eliot Hospital, United Kingdom

³Resident Urologist, Institute of kidney diseases, Peshawar, Pakistan

⁴Senior House Officer, Saint Luke General Hospital, Kilkenney, Ireland

⁵Senior House Officer, Tallaght University Hospital, Dublin, Ireland

⁶Geriatric Fellow, Rusell Hall Hospital, United Kingdom

⁷Resident Physician, Abbottabad Teaching Hospital, Abbottabad, Pakistan

Citation: Kamran Ahmad, Aima Yousaf, Usama Saeed, Yasir Ali, Shahzad Zafar, Waqar Ali, et al. Unraveling the Uncommon: Perianal Plasmablastic Lymphoma in an HIV-Negative Patient with Chronic Hepatitis C: A Case Report. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2024;3(5):1-5.

Received Date: 14 May, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 17 May, 2024; **Published Date:** 19 May, 2024

***Corresponding author:** Kamran Ahmad, Resident Physician, Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar, Pakistan

Copyright: © Kamran Ahmad, Open Access 2024. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour* (ICMCRJ) (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

We present the case of a 41-year-old man who, despite being HIV-negative, developed a rare and aggressive form of lymphoma called plasmablastic lymphoma (PBL) in the perianal region. Initially thought to be a common perianal fistula, the condition worsened over time despite multiple surgeries. Eventually, a biopsy revealed PBL. What's notable is the patient's co-existing chronic hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection, which is rarely associated with PBL in non-HIV patients. Prompt recognition led to chemotherapy treatment. This case emphasizes the importance of considering unusual diagnoses in chronic conditions and the need for further exploration into potential associations between HCV and rare lymphomas.

Keywords: Plasmablastic lymphoma; Perianal fistula; HIV-negative; HCV-positive; Rare disease; Diagnostic challenges

INTRODUCTION

Plasmablastic lymphoma (PBL), a subtype of diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, often associated with individuals infected with HIV. It is one of the aggressive and rare variants, most commonly present in oral cavity, gastrointestinal tract and lymph node.^[1] PBL has frequently been seen in patients who have had an underlying immunosuppressive state such as solid organ transplantation^[2] and lymphoproliferative or autoimmune disorders.^[3]

Anal PBL is rare with only 10 reported cases. Common causes of perianal fistula include abscesses, venereal diseases, radiations, trauma; and malignancy. Among malignancies; squamous cell carcinoma is the commonest, with lymphomas being infrequent in such locations.^[4] In HIV-negative patients. We are presenting this case of

HIV-negative and HCV-positive PBL as a cause of perianal fistula. Moreover, the scarcity of disease often delays its diagnosis. Yet, its association with hepatitis C virus is not established in non-immunocompromised.

CASE REPORT

A 41-year-old male, HCV positive, presented with a history of perianal discharge and discomfort for the last 4 years. According to the patient, he noticed mucous discharge in the perianal region, related to sudden onset of right lower limb pain and weakness, which was diagnosed as perianal fistula.

His past history revealed that he was operated three times as a perianal fistula. But, now patient had a non-healing ulcer in right buttock region, progressively increased in size over the period of four months, associated with fecal and pus discharge through it, in association with a history of weight loss.

On local examination, about 15 x 7 cm, polypoid mass in the right lower medial quadrant of gluteal region in the previous incision site, showing mucoid discharge and fungal infection in central region on inspection (shown in [Figure 1](#)). He had restricted movements at right hip joint, with in ability to fully flex and internally rotate the right thigh. Digital rectal exam showed hard mass on right lateral wall about 4 cm from anal verge. Lymph nodes were palpable in right inguinal region.

Basic metabolic profile, liver function tests, renal function tests and coagulation profile were all normal. Chest radiograph was normal. His viral profile showed anti-HCV positive on ELISA, whereas he was HIV-negative on PCR.

A MRI pelvis without contrast showed an ulcer in the parasagittal soft tissues of right buttock, measuring approx. 14cm in craniocaudal, 8cm in anteroposterior and 6cm in transverse dimensions, causing displacement of anorectum towards left side. There is a fistulous opening in right side of rectal wall, 5 cm from anal verge (shown in [Figure 2](#)). Mass also causes compression of right common iliac vessels at right hip with enlarged right inguinal lymph nodes.

A wedge biopsy of about 2 x 1 x 1 cm of non-healing ulcer was taken and sent for histopathology, which came out to be tumor arranged in sheets, composed of oval cells with eccentric nuclei, and prominent nucleoli and marked atypia, suggestive of plasmablastic lymphoma. Immunohistological stains were positive for CD138, CD4, EBER, LCA and Kappa (shown in [Figure 3](#)).

He was sent to oncologist for further management where they planned for CHOP regime.

Figure 1. Showing a polypoid mass on the previous incision site with fungal infection on right buttock

Figure 2. Mass in the right buttock (*black arrows*) in the sagittal section, mass with fistula (*white arrows*) in the coronal section of MRI.

Figure 3. Tumor cells arranged in sheets, composed of oval cells with eccentric nuclei, and prominent nucleoli and marked atypia, suggestive of Plasmablastic Lymphoma

DISCUSSION

Plasmablastic lymphoma is an aggressive and rare variant of diffused large B-cell lymphoma and accounts for approximately 3% of all HIV related non-Hodgkin lymphomas^[5], and was first described in 1997 in the oral cavity of an HIV-positive patient. In fact, in the initial report, 15 of the 16 patients (94%) who had PBL reported were infected with HIV.^[6] About 76 cases were reported in HIV- negative patients. Of 66 patients who had extranodal involvement, oral cavity involvement was reported in 14 (21%), gastrointestinal in 13 (20%), soft tissue in 11 (17%), and bone marrow involvement in 10 (15%)^[7] Anal Plasmablastic Lymphoma is very rare, a case published by Tajudeen, Anal plasmablastic lymphoma is usually associated with HIV.^[8] However, in our case patient was HIV negative which makes it a very unique and rare presentation.

The most common symptoms of perianal lymphoma are per rectal bleeding, pain and tenesmus.^[9]

Moreover, it was newly diagnosed HCV-positive patient and was not treated before. Studies showed that hepatitis C virus is linked with diffused large B-cell lymphoma with an odds ratio of 2.24.^[10] large B-cell lymphoma, processes may involve can be:

1. B-cell activation by interaction to HCV-receptor,
2. Proliferation of B-cells in response to HCV antigen and
3. Direct infection of B-cells by HCV permitting it to replicate with co-infection with any other virus.^[11]

Our case report indicated immunological markers i.e. CD138 and EBER, which are positive in 87% and 50% respectively, in HIV-negative PBL.^[12] To summarize the case, it's a rare malignancy mostly related with immunocompromised patients, but can occur in patients without any immunosuppressed state. However, its treatment is under trials and effective in terms of HIV-negative is CHOP regimen (cyclophosphamide, hydroxydaunorubicin, vincristine sulfate and prednisone). Additionally, immunological markers are tested to help in forming of targeted drugs. We highlighted a rare possibility of association between HCV and PBL and it would like to trigger more work to establish or exclude this association.

CONCLUSION

This case report highlights the rarity and diagnostic challenges of plasmablastic lymphoma (PBL), particularly when presenting in HIV-negative patients and involving unusual sites like the perianal region. The association between chronic hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection and PBL in non-immunocompromised individuals adds complexity to the understanding of its pathogenesis. Prompt recognition of PBL is crucial for timely intervention and improved outcomes. Further research is warranted to elucidate the underlying mechanisms linking HCV infection to PBL and to explore targeted therapeutic options for this aggressive lymphoma subtype in HIV-negative patients.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We express our gratitude to our supervisor and registrar of the ward for their invaluable assistance in collecting patient data and aiding in the diagnosis process. Their guidance and expertise significantly contributed to the completion of this case report.

REFERENCES

1. Jorge Castillo, Liron Pantanowitz, Bruce J Dezube. HIV-associated plasmablastic lymphoma: Lessons learned from 112 published cases. Am J Hematol. 2008;83(10):804-9.
2. J Borenstein, F Pezzella, K C Gatter. Plasmablastic lymphomas may occur as post-transplant lymphoproliferative disorders. Histopathology. 2007;51(6):774-7.
3. Ji Eun Kim, Young A Kim, Wook Youn Kim, Chul Woo Kim, Young Hye Ko, Geon Kook Lee, et al., Human immunodeficiency virus-negative plasmablastic lymphoma in Korea. Leuk Lymphoma. 2009;50(4):582-7.
4. Firoozeh Isfahani, Surabhi Amar, Harikrishna Dave, Daniel Gridley. Plasmoblastic Lymphoma as Cause of Perianal Fistula: A Case Report and Literature Review. J Int Assoc Provid AIDS Care. 2015;14(1):17-20.
5. B Guan, X Zhang, H Ma, H Zhou, X Zhou. A meta-analysis of highly active anti-retroviral therapy for treatment of plasmablastic lymphoma. Hematol Oncol Stem Cell Ther. 2010;3(1):7-12.
6. H J Delecluse, I Anagnostopoulos, F Dallenbach, M Hummel, T Marafioti, U Schneider, et al., Plasmablastic Lymphomas of the Oral Cavity: A New Entity Associated With the Human Immunodeficiency Virus Infection. Blood. 1997 ;89(4):1413-20.

7. Jorge J Castillo, Eric S Winer, Dariusz Stachurski, Kimberly Perez, Melhem Jabbour, Cannon Milani, et al. HIV-Negative Plasmablastic Lymphoma: Not in the Mouth. Clin Lymphoma Myeloma Leuk. 2011;11(2):185-9.
8. Muhammed Tajudeen, Souradeep Dutta, Ankit Jain, Bheemanathi Hanuman Srinivas, Vishnu Prasad Nelamangala Ramakrishnaiah. A rare case of hiv-associated plasmablastic lymphoma of anal canal. Cureus. 2021;13(9):e17782.
9. Ana Maria Stapasolla Vargas Garcia, Marlei Sangali, Antoninho Jose Tonatto Filho, Caroline Lara, Cibele Corbellini Rosa da Silva, Marcos Paulo Barreto Saturnino, et al., Primary extraperitoneal rectum lymphoma in AIDS patient. Journal of Coloproctology. 2020;40:175-8.
10. Silvia de Sanjose, Yolanda Benavente, Claire M Vajdic, Eric A Engels, Lindsay M Morton, Paige M Bracci, et al. Hepatitis C and Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma Among 4784 Cases and 6269 Controls From the International Lymphoma Epidemiology Consortium. Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol. 2008;6(4):451-8.
11. Fabrizio Marcucci, Alfonso Mele. Hepatitis viruses and non-Hodgkin lymphoma: epidemiology, mechanisms of tumorigenesis, and therapeutic opportunities. Blood. 2011;117(6):1792-8.
12. Jorge J Castillo, Michele Bibas, Roberto N Miranda, The biology and treatment of plasmablastic lymphoma. Blood. 2015;125(15):2323-30.